

Performance Observation of Proactive and Reactive Routing Protocols with Increasing the Connections

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Abstract: - Mobile Ad-hoc network (MANET) is type of wireless network in which group of mobile nodes cooperate to forward the data packets to their neighbours without using centralized authority or any physical medium like cables or base station. It is fully wireless network. The MANET follows the different type of routing protocols, which can be categories mainly into two forms are reactive routing protocol and proactive routing protocols. In this paper, we have taken two different routing protocols one is reactive (AODV) and another one is proactive (DSDV). Performance evaluated of these on the basis of different matrices such as Throughput, Normalized routing load and packet delivery ratio. The simulation has been successful done on network simulator-2 and awk script is used for calculation the value different parameters.

Keywords: AODV, DSDV, MANET, SANET and Ns-2

1. Introduction

A wireless network is a type of network, whose communicating devices are connected to each other with the wireless links. All the devices must be in communication range of each other. We have chooses the wireless network because it does not depends on wires or cable, can install easily, and mostly useful for hilly areas where wired connection not possible [1]. Wireless network can be divided in to two following forms which are:

1. Wired-cum-wireless network
2. Ad-hoc Network

Wired-cum-wireless networks are the type of network, which is based on central co-ordinating network where all wireless devices are controlled by a central administration. Ad-hoc network is another type of wireless network which is completely infrastructure-less network.

Ad-hoc network can also be dividing into two categories such as:

1. Static Ad-hoc Network
2. Mobile ad-hoc Network

Static Ad-hoc Network (SANET):- A network where geographical locations of nodes are fixed means it does not show the mobility called SANET.

Mobile Ad-hoc Network (MANET):- A mobile ad-hoc network is an infrastructure less self configuring network, which has frequently changing topology and no dependency of any control module [2]. In the MANET nodes location are not fixed so this network is called mobile ad-hoc network. Due to frequently variation of topology, routing maintenance is more difficult than static ad-hoc network. We are showing simple block diagram of MANET is below.

Fig1.1:- Mobile Ad-hoc Network

2. Routing in MANET

Routing provides robustness and efficient data transmission in the network. MANET uses the different routing protocols, which can be further divided into two basic types which are reactive routing protocols and proactive routing protocols [3]:

Fig 2.1:- Routing Protocols in MANET

Reactive Routing Protocol: - The entire on-demand routing protocols are reactive routing protocols where route discovery can be processed is on-demand. In the other words all the nodes provides route the when someone request for it.

Proactive Routing Protocols: - In this type of routing protocols, all the communicating devices periodically maintain their routing tables. For an

example, whenever a node wants to communicate to other nodes, it will check their routing table and sends the data toward the destination.

3. Purpose of Routing

The main purpose of routing is to handle the data flow into the network. Routing protocols is also specifies the how routers can share the data into the networks. The basic functions of routing protocols are as follows:

1. It is used to find the route to the destination.
2. Another is to provide the reliability of delivering the message to the correct destination.

We have taken two routing protocol from the proposed routing protocol are AODV as a reactive and DSDV as a proactive routing protocol.

3.1 Ad-hoc On Demand Distance Vector Routing (AODV)

AODV is reactive routing protocol which is expanded version of DSDV and DSR where route calculation is on demand whenever entries of destination node are not available in the routing table. Due to on demand routing the traffic on the network will be minimum. It does not allow the other extra useless routing. For creation of multiple routes, AODV enable those nodes which want to establish the connection to each other. It uses the sequence numbers for avoiding the problem of count-to-infinity. Whenever a node sends the route request to the destination nodes, it will reply with a sequence number [2][4]. According to the sequence number source can choose the right route to the destination node. AODV works on mostly three messages route request (RReq), route reply (RRep) and the route error (RErr). This also uses the user datagram protocol used for discovery and maintenance of route. In the AODV running protocol nodes keeps only the information of next node towards the destination.

In the AODV, a node wish to sends the data packets to the destination node, it will check the routing table and search the correct route to the destination. If searched entry is available, then nodes follow the available path but if the correct information is missing in their routing table, it will be generates and broadcast the route request (RReq) type control message to their neighbours. This control message must be transmitted by those nodes which has requirement of shortest path to destination. This control message contains the following information:

Table 1.1

Route Request			
Source IP	Destination IP	Known Sequence no. to Destination	Hop Count

Route request is also contains the Route request ID, which is attached together with the source IP address. This ID is used to universally identify a required route. It is also used for search the duplicates. In the AODV each node maintains the sequence number whether routing tables is updated or not. All the nodes have to create backward path before forwarding the RReq. The path is useful for replying to previous nodes. After rebroadcasting the RReq nodes will update the value of hop count. If the valid route does not exist in the path, intermediate nodes having a legal route [5]. These nodes reply with a unicast message. All the nodes frequently broadcast the HELLO messages to their neighbours. Links between the sender and receiver considered as failed link if the HELLO messages does not received by destination node. Link failure is type of local repair mechanism which is used for inform this failure information to all the about failure link by sending RErr (Route error) message. Sender may reinitiate the route discovery process by broadcasting RReq.

3.2 Destination Sequence Distance Vector Routing

DSDV is a type of routing protocol which is proactive in nature. In the DSDV each and every node maintains the local information of network topology. It is based on bellman ford algorithm. In DSDV running network each node use the control message and maintains their routing information in the form of tables. The routing information contains the information about next hop address, cost matrix and the sequence number. The sequence number is decided by the destination node. The cost matrix is used to determine the hop count which shows how many hops travelled by a packet.

In the DSDV nodes use the two types of mechanism like periodic update mechanism and trigger update mechanism [6]. These mechanisms are used to forward the updated routing information by the nodes to their all neighbours. Because of the periodic updates, loops are created in the network. For eliminating the loops DSDV uses the sequence numbers which is randomly selected by the nodes. Nodes don't have the permission to change the sequence number of other nodes [7]. These sequence number must be incremented by periodically updates

of a node. There are two types of update mechanism are normal updates and expiry route updates. In the normal update an even sequence number is selected by a node when it transmits a message.

Route expiry updates are used when the route is expires. In the condition of route expiry, node(s) increments the sequence number by an odd value [18]. So the corresponding entry will be deleted from the routing table by a node which found that odd sequence number.

3.3 Optimized Link State Routing Protocol (OLSR)

It is one of a proactive routing protocol, expansion of classical link state routing. As the working of classical link state routing, it has message overhead problem where each node retransmits the first received message. It is also required more control, and communicating links. As these drawbacks of classical link state routing, an optimized protocol has been provided called optimized link state routing protocol where three optimizations has been done. The optimizations are following[9]:

1. Election of MPRs
2. Minimum use of control messages
3. Minimum use of connecting links

OLSR protocol uses the MPRs (multipoint relays) as a matrix to finding the shortest path where only MPRs have permission to forward the data towards the destination nodes. Rule for selection of MPR nodes is, each 2-hop neighbour must be covered by a node. That node has been selected as the MPR node. MPR shows the greater willingness to carry the traffic in to whole network during the flooding process. Due to the selected node it minimizes the control messages and MPRs also select those links which are connected to itself and its selectors for giving their MPR selectors information by the use of topology control messages. We are showing OLSR flooding process by following figure:

Fig:-3.1 OLSR Flooding

We are showing a scenario in which a node S selects subset of neighbours (A, C, G, and E) as MPRs from

their neighbour set (A, B, C, D, E, F, G, and H). This subset of neighbour will be covered all the two hop neighbours. This process is called flooding process.

So this way limited numbers of nodes participates in the routing process. Each node maintains following repository to perform routing:

Link Set - It stores the information about links.

Neighbour Set and 2-hop Neighbour Sets - It keeps the information about neighbour and 2-hop neighbour set.

MPR and its Selector Sets - It keeps the information of set of selected node and their selector's node.

Topological Information Base- It keeps the whole topological information.

Routing Table- Routing table stores the information about the shortest route to any destination.

Protocol Functioning:

Overall functioning of OLSR is mostly depends on following steps:

Link Sensing: In this link sensing all the nodes broadcast and exchanges the HELLO messages and performs the link sensing and maintains Local Link Set. The discovered links may be symmetric or asymmetric.

Neighbour Detection: In the OLSR, HELLO messages is also used to maintain the information of Neighbours and 2-hop neighbour set, MPR and its selector set.

MPR Computation: This is performed to find out a subset from neighbour nodes which has willing to forward routing packets. These MPR nodes choose as they cover all 2-hop neighbour of any node.

Topology Discovery: In the topology discovery Topology Control (TC) messages are used. Each selected node called MPRs advertise to its MPR selectors using TC message.

Routing Table Computation: The information which is diffused in the network by these TC messages will help to compute routing table.

Simulation parameters

We have taken three performance matrices, such as packet delivery ratio, Normalized routing load and the Throughput. These are very helpful to us to know which protocol's performance is good or poor.

4. Simulation Experiments

Packet Delivery Rate: It is shows the number of successfully delivered packets at the destination to the whole data packets generated by sender or source.

Throughput: It is the main parameter which shows the speed of transfer of data. It is the rate of successfully transmitted data packets in a unit time in the network during the simulation.

Normalized Routing Load: It is defined as the total number of routed packets required for per data packet delivered at the destination.

We have created scenario 39 numbers of wireless nodes in the area taken in 1106x602m². All the simulation parameters and their values are shown in following table.

Table 3.1

Parameter	Value
Routing Protocol	DSDV, AODV and OLSR
Mac protocol	IEEE 802.11
Terrain Size	1101×602M ²
Number of Nodes	39
Propagation Model	Two Ray Ground Model
Simulation Time	250s
Antenna Type	Omni Antenna

Statistical Analysis

Simulation Results:

We have successfully done our simulation on network simulator-2.35. Main aim of this study to know the performance of table driven and on-demand routing protocols. Different types of performance metrics are taken to evaluate and compare the performance routing protocols of mobile ad-hoc network. We are showing the results for DSDV, AODV and OLSR routing protocol on the basis of PDR, Throughput and Normalized Routing Load in the low and high traffic environment are shown in the graphical form and tabular forms:

Table 4.1

Performance in Less Traffic

PROTOCOL	PDR	NRL	Throughput
AODV	L	A	L
DSDV	H	L	H
OLSR	A	H	A

Table 4.2

Performance in High Traffic

PROTOCOL	PDR	NRL	Throughput
AODV	L	H	L
DSDV	A	A	H
OLSR	H	L	A

Where L, H and A is Low, High and Average respectively.

Packet Delivery Ratio

Fig:-4.1

Instantaneous Throughput

Fig:-4.2

Normalized Routing Load

5. Conclusion

In this paper we have described the performance of three routing protocols with increasing the number of connections to know how low and high traffic will affects the performance of the network. So we have taken the two proactive routing protocols such as DSDV and OLSR and AODV as a reactive routing protocol. All the results shows that DSDV and OLSR have less throughput and high packet delivery ratio in high traffic connection as than a AODV. Whereas

these proactive routing protocols have high throughput and high packet delivery ratio as compared to AODV in the low traffic networks. All results are presented in this paper is obtained with 40 nodes AODV DSDV and OLSR running scenario with 5,10,15,20 and 25 FTP connections.

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